

Bank Distress Prediction Model for Botswana

V NIRANJAN REDDY, ASSISTANT PROFESSOR, anjanreddymsc@gmail.com

K RAVI, ASSISTANT PROFESSOR, kollamadaravi111@gmail.com

C OBILESU, ASSISTANT PROFESSOR, chitraobul@gmail.com

Department of Mathematics, Sri Venkateswara Institute of Technology,
N.H 44, Hampapuram, Rappthadu, Anantapuramu, Andhra Pradesh 515722

Abstract

"Financial distress" may signify various things, but in common use, it denotes a bad financial situation. There are three types of banks in Botswana: commercial, development, and savings. While it's true that several of these banks have been struggling, none of them have really gone down. As a distress indicator, the CAMELS ratings are used by the Bank of Botswana. Scores between 1 and 5 make up the CAMELS ratings; a score of 1 indicates excellent performance, while a score of 5 indicates a high risk of bank collapse and the critical need to fix the problem immediately. In this analysis, a score of 1-3 indicates a healthy bank, while a score of 4-5 indicates a troubled bank. The research examined the causes of bank distress in Botswana using secondary data sources from 2015 to 2019, inclusive. The eleven banks who took part in the research provided the data via their audited financial statements and yearly reports. Analysis was conducted using panel data logistic regression. A bank's non-performing loans (NPL) ratio and return on equity (ROE) were determined to be the most significant indicators of potential troubles in the research.

Keywords: Financial institution distress, logistic regression, panel data, and CAMELS.

Introduction

This work aims to fill that knowledge gap by analysing the factors that contribute to bank

distress in Botswana and developing a model to forecast when such a crisis will occur.

When a bank is in trouble because it can't pay its bills or live up to its promises to its clients, investors, and the neighbourhood it was founded in, we say that the bank is distressed. In order to ensure that banks are solvent and running well, the Bank of Botswana (BOB) keeps an eye on their liquidity, provisioning, risk management methods, managerial adequacy, and governance structures (BOB Banking Supervision Annual Report [1]). In the aftermath of the global financial crises and bank collapses, the CAMELS rating system has emerged as a crucial instrument for assessing the overall performance of banks, along with other performance metrics. Research by Khokher and Alhabshi [2] used logistic regression to identify critical capital adequacy metrics and other factors that accurately forecast Islamic bank distress. The results indicated that the majority of the conventional CAMELS indicators were applicable to the study of Islamic bank distress. Three listed commercial banks in Botswana were examined in a research by Sathyamoorthi et al. [3] that used the CAMEL model to assess their financial performance. The results showed that the banks were heavily indebted, but their

liquidity situation was good. The liquidity ratio of total customer deposits to total assets showed a substantial positive

Bank Distress Impact

When it comes to maintaining monetary stability on a global scale, financial institutions are crucial. The expenses of saving a bank that is about to collapse are significant. The whole financial system and economy are at risk of collapsing if one troubled bank threatens financial stability. There is an obvious need to create early warning models to anticipate banking crises and specific bank collapses due to the crucial role that banks play in maintaining financial stability. These unique characteristics need to have early warning systems in place that use publicly accessible indicators at both the bank and national levels to identify potentially troubled banks in the event that certain conditions are met. Between 1984 and 1989, the regulatory authorities in Kenya liquidated or took over two local banks and one hundred and ten non-bank financial institutions (NBFIs) (Brownbridge [10]). In 1993 and 1994, five more local banks and ten more NBFIs were taken over. According to Brownbridge [10], the Bank of Zambia (BOZ) shuttered three local banks in 1995, with non-performing loans being one of the reasons given for the institutions' collapse or difficulties. This is in addition to the closures of banks in Kenya. Studying the impact of bank distress on the economy, Adeyefa et al. [11] found that the ratio of non-performing loans to total loans significantly hampered economic

development in Nigeria. According to Claessens [12], macroeconomic concerns were the main cause of the banking crisis that hit Chile from 1981 to 1983, impacting around 60% of the country's entire loan portfolios. More so, according to Claessens [12], the number of banks was cut in half and the number of financing businesses was cut in half in 1984 due to liquidations and rehabilitations. An early-warning system to identify bank failures was necessary due to the increase in the frequency of bank failures induced by the economic crisis in Turkey, particularly between November 2000 and February 2001 (Toktas-Palut [13]). Toktas-Palut [13] used logistic regression and neural networks to build models that might predict Turkish bank collapses as much as three years in advance. The goal of the early warning system was to prevent such failures. Toktas-Palut [13] discovered that neural network models outperformed logistic regression models in terms of predictive power, and that a bank's capital adequacy, asset quality, liquidity position, profitability, and income expenditure structure are indicators of its likelihood of failure at a posterior time. New evidence suggests that the COVID-19 epidemic causes a number of problems for financial institutions, the most significant of which is an increase in default rates (Barua, 2014). The

epidemic is going to make an already bad position in Bangladesh's financial industry much worse. Lukas [14].

CAMELS Evaluation Method
The CAMELS rating system is a globally accepted method of assessing the riskiness of financial institutions using their financial statements; it was first created in the United States (Prachi [15]). According to Prachi [15], the idea evolved from the 1979 US Uniform Financial Institutions Rating System (UFIRS) CAMEL rating. The Federal Reserve and the Office of the Comptroller of the Currency (OCC) revised it in 1995 to include the sixth factor, "sensitivity," to it. According to Prachi [15], the six parts come together to create the word CAMELS. For each financial institution, a Bank Examiner will award a CAMELS grade depending on how well they handle market risk, the quality of their assets, their management, their profitability, and their liquidity. According to Mishkin [16], when a bank's CAMELS rating is very poor, the regulator may take formal procedures like stop and desist to modify the bank's conduct or even shut the bank. The Capital Adequacy (C) metric measures how well a financial institution meets the requirements for its minimum capital reserve. The grade is determined by regulators by looking at the capital situation of the financial institution both now and over a period of years. The first group is "Asset Quality," which measures how well a bank's assets are doing. The quick depreciation of high-risk assets highlights the significance of asset quality.

The capacity of a company's upper management to foresee and respond to

financial crises is reflected in its management capability (M). The business

Earnings (E): These help to evaluate an institution's long term viability. A bank needs an appropriate return to be able to grow its operations and maintain its competitiveness.

Liquidity (L): For banks, liquidity is essentially important, as the lack of liquid capital can lead to a bank run. This category of CAMELS examines interest rate risk and liquidity risk. Liquidity risk is defined as the risk of not being able to meet present or future cash flow needs without affecting day-to-day operations.

Sensitivity (S): Measures an institution's sensitivity to market risks. Sensitivity reflects the degree to which earnings are affected by interest rates, exchange rates, and commodity prices.

In this study, historical financial distress was calculated using the CAMELS Rating. The rating of individual banks is done along the 5 key parameters being; Capital Adequacy, Asset Quality, Management Quality, Earnings, Liquidity and Sensitivity. The banks are rated on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1-3 being the best (healthy) banks and 4-5 being the distressed (unhealthy) banks.

The best (healthy) bank is the bank with the strongest performance and risk management practices relative to the institutions size, while the distressed (unhealthy) bank is the bank with the least performance and risk management practices relative to the

institutions size.

Table 1 and Table 2 below show the ratios used for computing each of the CAMELS parameters and the description of the composite range, respectively.

Table 1. CAMELS parameters and ratios for bank performance analysis

CAMELS Parameters	Ratios / Formula
Capital Adequacy Ratio	$(\text{Tier 1 Capital} + \text{Tier 2 Capital}) / \text{Risk Weighted Assets}$
Asset Quality Ratio	$\text{Non-Performing Loans} / \text{Total Loans}$
Management Efficiency	$\text{Cost} / \text{Income}$
Earnings Ability (ROA) Earnings Ability (ROE)	$\text{Net Income} / \text{Total Assets}$ $\text{Net Income} / \text{Total Equity}$
Liquidity (TL/TD) Liquidity (CA/TA)	$\text{Total Loans} / \text{Total Deposits}$ $\text{Circulating Assets} / \text{Total Assets}$
Sensitivity Ratio	$\text{Financial Securities} / \text{Total Assets}$

Source: Babar [17].

Table 2. Composite range of CAMELS rating

Rating	Composite Range	Description	Meaning
1	1.00-1.49	Strong	Basically sound in every aspect Findings are of minor nature and can be handled routinely Resistant to external economic and financial disturbances No cause for supervisory concern
2	1.50-2.49	Satisfactory	Fundamentally sound Findings are of minor nature and can be handled routinely Stable and can withstand business fluctuations well Supervisory concerns are limited to the extent that findings are corrected
3	2.50-3.49	Fair	Financial, operational or compliance weaknesses ranging from moderately severe to unsatisfactory Vulnerable to the onset of adverse business conditions Easily deteriorate if actions are not effective in correcting weaknesses Supervisory concern and more than normal supervision to address inefficiencies
4	3.50-4.49	Marginal	Immoderate volume of serious financial weakness Unsafe and unsafe conditions may exist which are not being satisfactory addressed Without corrections, these conditions could develop further and impair future viability High potential for failure Close supervision surveillance and a definite plan for correcting deficiencies
5	4.50-5.00	Unsatisfactory	High immediate or near term probability failure Severity of weaknesses is so critical that urgent aid from stockholders or other financial sources is necessary Without immediate corrective actions, will likely require liquidations, merger or acquisition.

Source: Bari [18].

1 The Modelling Approach

For this study, the CAMELS rating will be used to measure historical bank distress and results will be analyzed using panel data logistic regression. The dependent variable was defined as the measured “bank distress/non-distress” and the Botswana banks were classified into two groups: distress (unhealthy,

non-prosperous) and non-distress (healthy, prosperous), using the calculated financial ratios in the CAMELS rating.

The data for 11 banks was collected from the annual reports and financial statements from the respective banks’ websites. The observation period was

from 2015 to 2019. The CAMELS rating for each of the banks was computed and classified into the below categories:

A CAMELS rating of 1-3 was classified as “Non-Distress”

A CAMELS rating of 4-5 was classified as

“Distress”

Using the ratios computed in Table 1 and the composite ranges provided in Table 2, the CAMELS rating results in Table 3 below were obtained.

Table 3. Banks CAMELS Rating

Bank Name	CAMELS Rating					Average Rating
	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	
ABSA (formerly Barclays)	3	3	3	3	3	3
Stanbic Bank Botswana	3	3	3	3	3	3
Botswana Savings Bank	3	3	3	3	3	3
First National Bank Botswana	3	3	3	3	3	3
Banc ABC	3	3	3	3	3	3
State Bank of India	3	3	3	3	3	3
First Capital Bank	3	3	3	3	3	3
Bank Gaborone	4	3	3	3	3	3
Standard Chartered Bank Botswana	3	3	4	3	3	3
Bank of Baroda	3	3	3	3	3	3
Botswana Building Society	3	3	4	4	4	4

Source: Computed ratings.

1.1 Data analysis

The main financial ratios for banks were selected by observing those most widely used in recent research, such as by Sree [19] and Gebreslassie [20]. Table 4 summarises the independent variables

used in the modelling process, and their a priori conditions.

With the independent variables explanation in Table 4, the logit regression (where Z is the natural

Table 4. Independent Variables Used and Explanations

Variable	Explanation	Calculation	A priori Signs
NPL_Ratio	Non Performing Loans Ratio	Non Performing Loans / Gross Advances	+
ROE	Return On Equity	Net Income / Average Equity	-
A.E	Assets to Equity Ratio	Assets / Equity	-
C.I	Cost to Income Ratio	Cost / Income	+
II.IE	Interest Income to Interest Expense Ratio	Interest Income / Interest Expense	-
LA.TD	Liquid Assets to Deposit Ratio	Liquid Assets / Deposits	-
NET.II.TI	Net Interest Income to Total Income	Net Interest Income / Total Income	-
NI.II.TI	Non-Interest Income to Total Income	Non-Interest Income to Total Income	-
NIM	Net Interest Margin	Non-Interest Income / Average Assets	-
I.A	Total Income to Average Assets Ratio	Total Income / Average Assets	-
CA.TA	Circulating Assets to Total Assets Ratio	Circulating Assets / Total Assets	-
TL.TA	Total Liabilities to Total Assets Ratio	Total Liabilities / Total Assets	+
CAR	Capital Adequacy Ratio	(Tier 1 Capital + Tier 2 Capital) / Risk Weighted Assets	-
ROA	Return On Assets	Net Income / Average Assets	-

Financial ratios based on the income statement and balance sheet were used to understand the connection between bank stability or instability. In this study, banks were assumed to face similar macroeconomic conditions.

The possible influence of each independent variable is as follows:

X 1=NPL Ratio (Non Performing Loans Ratio): Substantial numbers of banks have failed mainly due to non-performing loans. Poor loan quality is amongst the root causes in the informational problems that afflict financial markets (Brownbridge [10]). Huge non-performing loans portfolio erodes the ability of banks to make profits (Ugani [21]). In a study by Gebrellassie [20], it was found out that the NPL ratio has statistically negative influence on the financial health of the banks. Moreover, the European Semester Thematic Factsheet [22] states that the NPL ratio shows by how much the quality of loans granted by banks has deteriorated, and the higher the ratio, the worse the quality of the assets and as a result the higher the expected losses.

X 2=ROE (Return on Equity): ROE is an indicator of banks' overall profitability. A high profitability suggests that banks are in a favourable position to increase their capital buffer in the immediate future, namely through retained earnings (European Semester Thematic Factsheet [22]). Asykin et al. [5] states that ROE has a negative and significant effect on financial distress.

X 3=A E (Financial Leverage): Asset / Equity indicates the relationship of the total assets of the bank to the portion owned by shareholders and it is an indicator of the leverage (debt) used to

finance the bank.

X 4=C I (Cost-to-Income): Total cost / total income measures the income generated per unit cost. That is, how expensive it is for the bank to produce a unit of output. The lower the C I ratio, the better the performance of the bank (Kumbirai and Webb [23]). On average distressed banks have a higher level of cost-to-income ratio (Poghosyan and Cihak [24]).

X 5=LA TD (Liquid Assets / Total Assets): Banks need to maintain a level of liquidity sufficient to meet current and future financial obligations (Babanskiy [25]). Therefore, the higher the LA TD ratio, the lower the probability of distress.

X 7=NET II TI (Net interest income to total income): Net interest income to total revenue ratio has statistically significant positive influence on the financial health of banks (Gebrellassie [20]).

X 8=NII TI (Non-Interest Income/ Total Income): Revenue income generated from the non-core activities by banks and financial institutions plays a vital role in its overall profitability. The higher the NII TI ratio the lower the probability of distress.

X 9=NIM (Net Interest Margin): A positive NIM indicates that an entity operates profitably, while a negative figure implies investment inefficiency. Credit risk tends to be positively associated with net interest margin.

X 10=I A (Total Income/Total Assets): A bank with a higher level of liquid assets is normally expected to earn less interest income and therefore a lower asset yield (Total income / Total Assets) (Sree [19]). Therefore, the higher the total income/total asset ratio, the higher the interest income earned, hence the higher the performance of the bank.

X 11=CA TA (Circulating Assets/ Total Assets): All the assets and resources that can be easily

converted to cash in a short period, also represents a bank's liquid assets.

X 12=TL TA (Total Liabilities/ Total Assets): TL TA ratio shows the percentage of assets that are being funded by debt. The higher the ratio is, the more financial risk there is in the bank.

X 13=CAR (Capital Adequacy Ratio): Banks with high debt and low level of capital relative to its assets are more prone to failure in the event of a financial crisis (Badalashvili [26]). CAR

has a negative and significant effect on financial distress (Asykin et al. [5]).

X 14=ROA (Return on Assets): It is used to measure the ability of a company to generate revenue from asset management. The higher the ROA, the lower the possibility of bank distress, therefore, the ROA has a negative effect on bank distress (Kowanda et al. [27]). (Asykin et al. [5]) also found out that ROA has a negative and significant effect on financial distress.

2 Data Analysis and Presentation

In order to detect multicollinearity among the independent variables, cross correlations were performed and the outcome is in Table 5. Total liabilities to total assets (TL TA) is highly correlated with the financial leverage ratio (A E), liquid assets to total deposit (LA.TD) ratio is highly correlated with circulating assets to total assets (CA TA) ratio and ROE is highly correlated to ROA . The correlation shall be dealt with in the modelling process.

Table 5. Multicollinearity Results

	A.E	C.J	CA.TA	CAR	I.A	IL.IE	LA.TD	NET.ILTI	NILTI	NIM	NPL.RATIO	ROA	ROE	T.TA
A.E	1													
C.J	-0.0431	1												
CA.TA	0.0870	-0.1785	1											
CAR	-0.6437	0.5150	-0.1851	1										
I.A	-0.1674	-0.2613	-0.1106	-0.2753	1									
IL.IE	-0.1763	-0.1858	-0.1240	-0.0222	0.6982	1								
LA.TD	-0.2068	-0.1498	0.8239	0.1669	-0.1996	-0.1957	1							
NET.ILTI	-0.1187	0.1055	0.3332	0.2268	-0.4005	-0.3185	0.4333	1						
NILTI	0.1187	-0.1055	-0.3332	-0.2268	0.4005	0.3185	-0.4333	-1.0000	1					
NIM	-0.2470	-0.1978	0.0626	-0.1442	0.7936	0.5209	0.0243	0.2251	-0.2251	1				
NPL.RATIO	-0.0422	-0.4256	0.1460	-0.1021	-0.1478	0.1001	0.3167	0.0094	-0.0094	-0.2028	1			
OA	-0.0639	-0.7652	0.1804	-0.2789	0.4301	0.4275	0.1785	-0.1351	0.1351	0.3520	0.2700	1		
ROE	0.0101	-0.5776	0.1962	-0.3704	0.5549	0.5061	0.0571	-0.2588	0.2588	0.3936	0.0650	0.8429	1	
TL.TA	0.8884	-0.2182	0.1601	-0.8425	0.0021	-0.0227	-0.2189	-0.2250	0.2250	-0.1460	0.0473	0.0865	0.2561	1

Taking the confidence level as 95% and then running the logistic regression analysis, the following results were obtained:

Table 6. Panel Data Logistic Regression Results

Driver	Coefficients	Standard Error	Wald	df	Significance	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower 95%	Upper 95%
NPL.RATIO	63.8018	29.0671	4.8180	1	0.0282	5.1143E+27	9.2645E+02	2.8233E+52
ROE	-19.8731	9.1147	4.7539	1	0.0292	2.3400E-09	4.0811E-17	1.3417E-01
CONSTANT	-4.9524	2.0136	6.0491	1	0.0139	7.0665E-03		

Given the above results, the resultant multiple logistic regression model was deduced to be:

$$Z = -4.9524 + 63.8018 * NPL.RATIO - 19.8731 * ROE \quad (5.1)$$

The above model shows that the major drivers of Probability of Distress (PD) in Botswana are NPL Ratio and ROE. NPL ratio has a coefficient of 63.8018 that is significant and positively correlated to PD, hence it increases the probability of distress of a bank. This implies that a 1-

unit increase in the NPL ratio results in a 63.8018 increase in Z and therefore an increase in the probability of distress assuming all other variables are held constant. The positive coefficient of the NPL ratio is in agreement with the a priori condition in Table 4 and the European Semester Thematic Factsheet [22] that

the higher the NPL ratio, the worse the quality of the assets, and consequently the higher the expected loss. Further, the results indicate that in line with economic theory, the PD is negatively correlated to ROE. Thus, empirical evidence suggests that ROE reduces probability of bank distress since a 1-unit increase in ROE results in a -19.8731 decrease in Z and therefore a decrease in the probability of distress when all other variables are held constant. The negative coefficient of the

ROE is in agreement with the a priori condition in Table 4 and also in agreement with Asykin et al. [5] that ROE has a negative and significant effect on financial distress. The intercept is -4.9524 and implies that in the absence of all the other drivers, all banks in the banking system of Botswana are in a non-distress state since the PD is 0.70%. This is in agreement with the initial statement that none of the banks in Botswana have actually failed.

Table 7. Critical Values Table

α	0.10	0.05	0.025	0.01	0.005	0.001
$C(\alpha)$	1.22	1.36	1.48	1.63	1.73	1.95

Fig. 1. K-S Test

Table 8. Kolmogrov-Smirnov Statistic

D_{N_1, N_2}	0.0202
N_1	55
N_2	18
$C(\alpha)$	1.36
$D(\alpha)$	0.3693

In this study, the model was developed using 100% of the sample, that is, $N_1 = 55$. For the validation, a randomly selected sample of one-third of the total sample was used, that is, $N_2 = 18$ as seen on Table 8. This validation sample comprised of 16 non-distressed observations and 2 distressed observations.

Since $\alpha=0.05$ and $0.0202 = D_{N_1, N_2} < D(\alpha) = 0.3693$ (as seen in Table 8), we fail to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, this implies that the two samples come from the same distribution.

Building Society in 2017 had a CAMELS rating of 4 meaning it was distressed, however, our model

redicted it with a probability of distress of 12.81% (non-distress). In 2018, Bank of Baroda, had a CAMELS rating of 3 (non-distress), however, our model predicted a probability of distress of 88.24% (distress). The model was able to predict both distress and non-distress of all other banks accurately, except for Botswana Building Society which was on average rated as a distressed bank but our model rated it on average as

a non-distressed bank. The actual result for all the banks are in line with the actual situation in Botswana at the present moment, that is, Botswana comprises of a non-distressed banking sector.

Table 9. Back Testing

Bank Name	CAMELS RATING					Average Rating	MODEL RATING					Average Rating	RISK LEVEL
	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019		2015	2016	2017	2018	2019		
ABSA (formerly Barclays)	3	3	3	3	3	3	0.38%	0.18%	0.12%	0.23%	0.12%	0.20%	Insignificant
Stanbic Bank Botswana	3	3	3	3	3	3	0.84%	0.22%	0.07%	0.06%	1.19%	0.48%	Insignificant
Botswana Savings Bank	3	3	3	3	3	3	0.31%	0.38%	0.27%	1.47%	0.16%	0.52%	Insignificant
First National Bank Botswana	3	3	3	3	3	3	0.07%	0.37%	2.01%	0.77%	0.57%	0.76%	Insignificant
Banc ABC	3	3	3	3	3	3	0.19%	0.19%	0.44%	1.92%	1.82%	0.91%	Insignificant
State Bank of India	3	3	3	3	3	3	2.61%	6.52%	0.81%	1.13%	0.31%	2.27%	Insignificant
First Capital Bank	3	3	3	3	3	3	1.84%	7.40%	0.42%	0.19%	0.10%	1.99%	Insignificant
Bank Gaborone	4	3	3	3	3	3	55.02%	6.62%	2.29%	2.51%	3.50%	13.99%	Modest
Standard Chartered Bank Botswana	3	3	4	3	3	3	1.09%	0.76%	97.70%	2.04%	1.09%	20.54%	Average
Bank of Baroda	3	3	3	3	3	3	2.93%	4.11%	3.13%	88.24%	21.34%	23.95%	Average
Botswana Building Society	3	3	4	4	4	4	3.01%	6.27%	12.81%	58.58%	91.27%	34.39%	Average

2.1.1 Prediction classification

The results in Table 10 show that 1 out of 55 observations was predicted as distressed, however, in actual fact it was not distressed, as a result 80% of the distresses were accurately predicted. On the other hand, there was 1 out of 55 observations that was

predicted as non-distressed, however, the observation was a distress in actual fact, as a result 98% of the observations predicted as non-distress were observed to be non-distressed. In overall, the accuracy of the regression model amounted to 96.4%.

Table 10. Prediction Classification

	Actual Distress	Actual Non-Distress	Percentage Correct
Predicted Distress	4	1	80%
Predicted Non-Distress	1	49	98%
Overall Percentage			96.4%

3 Conclusion

The research looked at the causes of bank failure in Botswana over a five-year period and found that nonperforming

loan ratio (NPL) and return on equity (ROE) are the key causes of bank failure, with NPL being the most important. The

economy is hurting when the nonperforming loan ratio rises because banks are struggling, and it's doing better when the return on equity rises. According to the AUROC, our model has a prediction strength of 98.4%, and the model's findings confirm that Botswana's banking industry is not in trouble. With a classification capability of 96.4%, the model is quite effective.

To help identify potentially troubled institutions, the Central Bank may use the model as an analytical early warning decision support tool. You may use the model to gauge bank distress in addition

to or instead of the CAMELS. Banks, investment firms, and individual individuals looking to invest in Botswana-based banks may all utilise the model.

The analysis was limited to the years 2015–2019 due to the fact that most banks did not have financial data for 2020. The COVID-19 epidemic caused a dramatic shift in the financial industry in 2020, so that year should be included in future studies. The evaluation of Botswana bank performance metrics is the next step in our investigation.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my supervisor Dr Victor Gumbo for the

continuous support of my research, for his motivation and patience.

Competing Interests

All authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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